

DESIGN CRITERIA FOR CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED MMC BOLT CONNECTORS

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SUMMARY: The bolt connector geometry is of general interest to mechanical engineers as it represents a wide range of applications. These components are generally used for transfer of static or dynamic loads. An analytical model has been developed to predict the stress distribution in the shoulder area of such a component. Experiments with two geometries and different materials, unreinforced and fibre reinforced aluminium, have been performed for the verification of the model.

Even though the tensile strength of fibre reinforced aluminium can be much higher than of unreinforced aluminium, 900 MPa compared to 400 MPa, the fibre reinforcement of such a component is not suitable to increase the UTS due to the brittle stress-strain behaviour of the composite. However, a significant improvement of the fatigue behaviour is possible.

KEYWORDS: Aluminium matrix composites, fibre reinforcement, bolt connectors, stress distribution.

INTRODUCTION

A common means of fixation of components in aeronautics and other applications are bolt connectors. The bolt connection of an aileron to the wing is one example. Large scale housings are often attached to other components by rather small connectors resulting in high local stresses. A potential application for CFRMs (Continuous Fibre Reinforced Metals) can be the local reinforcement of such highly stressed areas.

Based on Hook's law an analytic model has been developed to predict the stress distribution in the shoulder area of continuous fibre reinforced bolt connectors. This model takes into consideration the geometry of the component and the anisotropy of the material.

The real stress distribution in continuous fibre reinforced aluminium has been measured with strain gauges and compared to the model. Two possibilities for improving the stress distribution in the shoulder area of these components have been tested in tension and fatigue.

THEORETICAL STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN FIBRE REINFORCED BOLT CONNECTORS

For specimens with a fibre arrangement as shown in *Fig.1* an analytic model for predicting the stress distribution in continuous fibre reinforced bolt connectors has been developed and presented at ICCM 11 [1]. Based on Hook's law and taking into consideration the geometry and the anisotropy we finally get Eqn 1.

Fig. 1: Geometry and fibre arrangement of the specimen investigated. The stress distribution in the shoulder area resulting from the applied load N is analysed by an analytic model.

$$\sigma_{II}(r) = \left\{ \frac{1}{2 \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) + \frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}} \left[\frac{1}{2 \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) + \frac{1}{\ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right)} \right]} \right\} \left[\frac{1}{R_{in}^2 \left(\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right)^2 - 1 \right)} \cdot r - \frac{2 \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \cdot \frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}} \right)}{R_{in} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right)^2 - 1 \right)} \right] \frac{N}{a} \quad (1)$$

$$\eta_{geom} = \frac{N}{\sigma_{IIin} \times 2a(R_{ex} - R_{in})} \quad (2)$$

If the geometrical effectiveness η is defined as the quotient of the applicable load N divided by the cross section $2a(R_{ex}-R_{in})$ and the maximum tensile strength of the material in fibre direction σ_{IIin} (Eqn 2) we get the influence of the geometry and the anisotropy as shown in *Fig.2*. It is obvious that the higher the anisotropy of the material, the higher the sensitivity of the effectiveness to the geometry. This statement is in good agreement with published results from continuous fibre reinforced polymers [2] or bulk

Fig. 2: Influence of geometry and anisotropy on the geometrical effectiveness. The higher the anisotropy of the material, the higher the sensitivity of the effectiveness to the geometry.

materials [3]. For bulk material the anisotropy factor E_{\parallel}/E_{\perp} is 1 and for unidirectional reinforced HS carbon fibre - epoxy it is at least 12.2. For HM carbon fibre – epoxy this factor can be up to 65. For the material investigated (Sumitomo Altex fibre in aluminium matrix) this factor is 1.4706.

However, comparing the measured stress distribution with those predicted by the analytic model, it is evident that some important parameters have not been taken into account. It is known from other publications [2] that an additional bending moment has to be considered in the shoulder area of such a component, and that this moment depends on the load applied, the geometry of the component and the stiffness in the shoulder area. The stiffer the component, the higher the bending moment.

From technical mechanics [4] we know that for a bent beam with rectangular cross section loaded by tension and bending the stress distribution can be described as shown in Eqn 3.

$$\sigma_x(r) = \frac{N}{a(R_{ex} - R_{in})} + \frac{2M_B}{a(R_{ex} + R_{in})(R_{ex} - R_{in})} \left[1 + \frac{1 - \frac{R_{in}}{2r} \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right)}{\frac{R_{ex} + R_{in}}{2(R_{ex} - R_{in})} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) - 1} \right] \quad (3)$$

The stress distribution resulting from the tensile loading has been discuss before, see Eqn 1. Therefore we only continue to discuss the stress distribution $\sigma_B(r)$ resulting from the bending moment, as shown in Eqn 4.

The bending moment is a function of the stiffness in the shoulder area of the component and the fit between the hole in the bolt-connector and the bolt itself. Therefore the loading can either be calculated numerically by finite elements' analysis or approached analytically. Three different loadings can be distinguished, simplifying the analytical model as shown in Fig.3. Chains, for example, usually have a very loose fit and therefore the load is transmitted very locally from one link to the next. For a medium good fit a constant loading over the cross section of the bolt can be assumed. For a good fit a pressures loading as for a pressure vessel is more appropriate. The holes of the components investigated have been machined so that hear the load transfer via pressure can be used.

Fig. 3: Bending moment as a function of the loading and the geometry of the bolt-connector [2]

We therefore get Eqn. 5 where C is a constant factor reflecting the significance of the bending moment.

$$\sigma_B(r) = \frac{2M_B}{a(R_{ex} + R_{in})(R_{ex} - R_{in})} \left[1 + \frac{1 - \frac{R_{in}}{2r} \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right)}{\frac{R_{ex} + R_{in}}{2(R_{ex} - R_{in})} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) - 1} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$M_B = -C \cdot N(R_{ex} - R_{in}) \quad (5)$$

From Eqn. 4 and 5 we get:

$$\sigma_B(r) = \frac{-2 C \cdot N}{a \cdot R_{in} \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right)} \left[1 + \frac{2 \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1 \right) \cdot \left\{ 1 - \frac{R_{in}}{2r} \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right) \right\}}{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right) \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) - 2 \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1 \right)} \right] \quad (6)$$

The stresses resulting from the bending moment have no impact on the load. Therefore a simple addition of these two stresses can be made as shown in Eqn. 7.

$$\sigma_T(r) = \sigma_{II}(r) + \sigma_B(r) \quad (7)$$

Due to the fact that the highest tensile stress should be expected in the face of the hole ($r = R_{in}$), from Eqn. 1, 2, 6 and 7 we finally get Eqn. 8:

$$\eta_{Geom} = \frac{1}{2 \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1 \right)} \left\{ \frac{1}{2 \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right)} + \frac{2C}{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right)} \cdot \left[\frac{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1 \right)^2}{\ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right) - 2 \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1 \right)} - 1 \right] + \frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}} \left[\frac{3 \frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1}{2 \ln \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right) \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1 \right)} + \frac{1 - 2 \frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}}{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \right)^2 - 1} \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

In the end the geometrical effectiveness depends on the geometry of the component (R_{ex}/R_{in}), the anisotropy of the material (E_{II}/E_{\perp}) and on the significance of the bending moment reflected by the factor C. For bulk material we get a good agreement of the calculated effectiveness to empirical results for a factor of $C = 0.065$, see Fig.4. The model shows a good agreement to empirical results for geometries with a ratio of $R_{ex}/R_{in} > 1.5$. Only for components with a big bolt diameter and a low width of the shoulder area the model predicts lower effectiveness than empirically measured.

Fig. 4: Dependence of the geometrical effectiveness on the geometry for isotropic materials ($E_{II}/E_{\perp} = 1$) as predicted from Eqn.8 compared to published empirical results [3].

EXPERIMENTS

Tensile Tests

Two different specimen geometries have been investigated. The first specimen geometry has been tested with a fully reinforced cross section of the shoulder area, a 47% reinforcement and for comparison in the unreinforced condition, with a ratio of $R_{ex}/R_{in} = 2.42$. The second geometry ($R_{ex}/R_{in} = 1.61$) has only been tested with a fibre reinforcement of the cross section of 76.5% (Fig. 5). For these specimens a surface layer in the face of the hole is unreinforced.

Fig. 5: The two specimen geometries investigated, without reinforcement, with 50% reinforcement and the same geometry fully reinforced with a ratio of 2.42 and geometry two with a ratio of 1.61. Additionally the load and the average tensile stress in the shoulder area is indicated.

Fig. 6: Stress and load versus displacement of the hydraulic cylinder. The positioning of the six strain gauges is shown on the right.

Unreinforced specimens have been tested for comparison and later on for discussion of the test results. The unreinforced specimens have been cast with the same aluminium alloy as

used for the fibre reinforced specimen as matrix material, a Al-Zn6-Mg1-Ag1 alloy. The stress distribution in the shoulder area of these specimens has been measured with six strain gauges. In *figure 6* the high plastifiability of the unreinforced material is clearly visible. The strain gauge 1 failed in an early stage of the measurement. Based on the curves of the other strain gauges it has been reconstructed. The specimen failed at a maximum load of 118 kN, which means an average tensile stress of 292 MPa. *Figure 7* shows the stress distribution for the pure elastic deformation (a) and immediately before failure (b). The theoretic model can only predict the stress distribution for purely elastic deformations. Therefore the theoretic stress distribution has only been included in *Figure 7a*.

Fig. 7: Stress distribution in the shoulder of a bolt connector in the purely elastic stage (including the theoretic distribution with $C = 0.065$) and immediately before failure of the component.

The fully fibre reinforced specimen failed at a maximum load of $N = 57$ kN, which means at only approx. 50 % of the maximum load of the unreinforced specimen. The main difference in the behaviour is that there is almost no plastification of the material until the crack is initiated in the face of the hole, see *Fig. 8 a*. After a quick crack propagation the specimen finally fails. Immediately before crack initiation there is a very inhomogeneous stress distribution with a peak stress of almost 1000 MPa in the face of the hole and a compressive stress of $\sigma = -50$ MPa at the back of the specimen, *Fig. 8 b*. Additionally the theoretic stress distribution as we get it from Eqn.7 for a factor $C = 0.2$ (valid for unidirectional reinforcement) is plotted.

One option for improving the stress distribution is to reinforce only the external section of the specimen, as shown in *Fig. 5*. In *Fig. 9a* we can see that immediately before failure the stress distribution has considerably been improved, with a plastification of the unreinforced section. However, the maximum load (106 kN) is not higher than the one for unreinforced specimens.

Another option for improvement of the stress distribution is the modification of the geometry by reducing the ratio R_{ex}/R_{in} . For a constant cross section this can be reached by using a bigger bolt diameter, *Fig. 5 Geom.2*. As shown in *Fig.10* we get some plastification in the small unreinforced section in the face of the hole. However, the overall load displacement curve shows an almost brittle behaviour. Compared to the geometry discussed before the stress distribution in the fibre reinforced section is much more linear but still very inhomogeneous, with a clear maximum in the face of the hole and considerable compressive stresses at the outside. If we compare the measured stress distribution to a theoretic stress distribution of a fully fibre reinforced component ($C = 0.2$) at the same load we get a reasonable good fit.

Fig. 8: Load and stress-displacement curve of a fully fibre reinforced specimen (a) and resulting stress distribution immediately before crack initiation in the face of the hole (b). Additionally the theoretic stress distribution for a factor of $C = 0.2$ is plotted.

Fig. 9: Load and stress-deflection curve of a partly fibre reinforced specimen (a) and resulting stress distribution immediately before (b) failure. The plastification of the unreinforced section, strain gauge 1 and 2, is clearly visible.

Fig. 10: Load and stress-deflection curve of a partly fibre reinforced specimen of geometry 2 (a) and resulting stress distribution immediately before (b) failure. Considerable compressive loading of the external sections of the specimen has been measured. Additionally the theoretic stress distribution for a fully fibre reinforced specimen is plotted showing the compressive loading of this section, too.

Fatigue Tests

Two unreinforced specimens cast with the same alloy (Al-Zn6-Mg1-Ag1) as the fibre reinforced ones have been tested for comparison. The maximum average tensile stress selected was $\sigma_{\max} = 125$ MPa with a ratio of $R = 0.1$ (tension-tension). One specimen failed after 4264 and the other after 1194 cycles, *Table 1*.

Table 1: Summary of fatigue test results as performed at the Giesserei-Institut and Aérospatiale

Specimen	Reinf. cross section [%]	Fibre fraction in the reinf. [%]	Geometry	Max. stress [MPa]	R ratio	No. of Cycles to failure
SP-U3	0		1	125	0.1	4264
SP-U4	0		1	125	0.1	1194
SP-36 *	100	50	1	125	0.1	153,820
SP-72	47	50	1	125	0.1	1637
SP-73	47	50	1	125	0.1	6640
SP-93	76.5	50	2	125	0.1	3018
SP-94	76.5	50	2	125	0.1	3507

* Specimen tested at Aérospatiale

The fatigue test results of the fully fibre reinforced component have been presented at ICCM-11 [1]. However, the test result of specimen SP-36 has been included in *Table 1*. This specimen failed after 153,820 cycles. Unfortunately this specimen has not been equipped with strain gauges so that details of the failure cannot be presented. The 47 % reinforced specimens showed a significant improvement in tensile strength compared to the fully reinforced specimen. However, in fatigue this specimen is inferior. In fatigue it shows a similar behaviour as the unreinforced specimen, *Figure 11*. The not closed hysteresis loop of cycle 1 indicates some plactical deformation especially in the area of strain gauge No. 1. The fibre reinforced section is only loaded up to 180 MPa (Strain gauge 3). After 1000 cycles the hysteresis loop looks very similar. There is a small accumulation of deformations, indicated by the displacement of the hysteresis loop. For the first cycle the loop had a displacement of $x_{\min} = 0.479$ mm and $x_{\max} = 1.014$ mm, for loop No. 1000 it is $x_{\min} = 0.5$ mm and $x_{\max} = 1.051$ mm. The peak load of the MMC is reduced to 150 MPa after 1000 cycles. *Figure 12* clearly shows that the crack is initiated in the unreinforced material in the face of the hole at 5200 cycles. The fibre reinforced section remains almost unloaded until the failure of the specimen.

Fig. 11: Hysteresis loop of cycle one a) and 1,000 b) of specimen SP-73. The strain gauges 1 and 2 are placed onto the unreinforced material and the strain gauges 3 to 6 on the fibre reinforced material.

Fig. 12: Strain of the first three strain gauges plotted over the number of cycles. The first two strain gauges are placed in the unreinforced material whereas strain gauge 3 is placed in the MMC.

CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical stress distribution predicted by the model developed does not completely fit to the stress distribution measured. However, it allows to predict the peak stress in the face of the hole and it is an easy tool to better understand how to improve a fibre reinforced bolt connector.

From the investigations presented there are two reasons why it is unlikely that a fibre reinforced bolt connector can be better in UTS than an unreinforced one. Unreinforced aluminium allows the plastification of the material, resulting in an almost constant loading of the whole cross section immediately before failure. The fibre reinforcement does not allow the plastical deformation of the component during loading. This means that there is an unfavourable stress distribution in the component until failure with a very high peak load of almost 1000 MPa in the face of the hole. The second reason is that the bending moment for the MMC component seems to be higher than for bulk material. There is a reasonable good fit to the measured stress distribution for a factor of $C = 0.065$ for bulk material and $C = 0.2$ for unidirectional fibre reinforcement. As we can see in *Figure 13* the sensitivity of the effectiveness to the geometry is reduced if the factor C is increased. In *Figure 13* additionally the two geometries investigated are indicated.

The main advantage of the fibre reinforced component compared to the unreinforced component is the improvement in fatigue behaviour. A selective reinforcement, compared to a full reinforcement, can improve the tensile strength of the component significantly, but it is not appropriate for improving the fatigue properties. The crack is initiated in the unreinforced material and the fibre reinforcement remains almost unloaded until the failure of the specimen. Therefore its fatigue behaviour is almost the same as for the unreinforced material.

A significant improvement of the effectiveness can be achieved if the bending moment is reduced. One option could be to use a 2-D fibre arrangement in the bolt connector. We will continue to investigate this application for a continuous fibre reinforcement, especially for the improvement of the fatigue behaviour of such components.

Fig. 13: Effectiveness of a bolt connector depending on the geometry, the bending moment and the anisotropy of the material.

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